

PARASITOLOGICAL sciences

MONITORING THE RESISTANCE TO ANTIHELMINTIC DRUGS

Khanmirzayev F.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y. Akhundov
Doctor of philosophy in medicine
section manager*

Janahmadova Sh.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y. Akhundov
Doctor of philosophy in medicine, associate professor
senior researcher*

Bandalizada G.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y. Akhundov
scientific researcher*

Aliyeva G.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y. Akhundov
scientific researcher*

Abbasova Y.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y. Akhundov
scientific researcher*

Darabi L.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y. Akhundov
department head of the polyclinic*

Bakhshiyeva S.

*Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y. Akhundov
senior laboratory assistant*

Abstract

Currently, resistance to the main antihelmintic drugs used in the treatment of human helminthiasis, such as mebendazole, albendazole, pyrantel, and pyrvinium pamoate, is increasingly observed. These antihelmintic drugs have been widely used in the treatment of helminthiasis for many years. The effectiveness of etiology treatment with these drugs has been studied by several researchers. For instance, low recovery rates were observed with albendazole (61% at 400 mg and 67% at 800 mg), levamisole (23% with repeated doses), pyrantel pamoate (30% with a single dose and 37% with repeated doses), and mebendazole (19% with a single dose and 45% with repeated doses).

In vitro methods for confirming susceptibility to antihelmintic drugs have not been sufficiently developed or standardized. The resistance of helminths to drugs can be assessed by the reduction in egg count in feces post-treatment, and the effect on eggs and larvae can also be evaluated. The primary aim is to assess the resistance to antihelmintic drugs. The methods available for monitoring resistance are outlined in the paper.

To date, counting helminth eggs in feces (CR) and determining the rate of reduction in egg count (ERR) after treatment with antihelmintic drugs are the methods commonly used for monitoring drug efficacy in helminthology. The study discusses the amount of sample taken for analysis, the analysis of results, and the relationship between the host and the parasite.

Keywords: helminths, antihelmintics, resistance to antihelmintics, in vitro methods.

Introduction

Human helminthiasis are one of the pressing issues in medical science and public health, accounting for over 90% of parasitic diseases encountered in humans [1]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 90% of the global population is infected with helminths [2]. The World Bank has reported that helminthiasis rank fourth in terms of economic damage, following diphtheria, tuberculosis, and ischemic heart disease.

Recently, resistance to some antihelmintic drugs has been observed, creating a need for new antihelmintic drugs and research into their effectiveness against helminths. Taking this into account, this review analyzes the results of published research on the resistance to antihelmintic drugs used in the treatment of human

helminthiasis. The factors contributing to the development of resistance, the molecular-genetic mechanisms of resistance, and the existing methods for detecting drug susceptibility are reconsidered. Some studies have shown that the effectiveness of treating certain human helminthiasis has decreased in recent years [3]. The development of resistance to current antihelmintic drugs is mainly due to their widespread use outside of medical supervision and improper dosing [1]. The parasite's response to the drug leads to genetic mutations. Currently, the main antihelmintic drugs used in the treatment of human helminthiasis, such as mebendazole, albendazole, pyrantel, and pyrvinium pamoate, show increased resistance. These drugs have been used for many years, and their effectiveness has been studied by several researchers. For instance:

- Albendazole: low recovery rates of 61% (400 mg) and 67% (800 mg)
- Levamisole: 23% (with repeated doses)
- Pyrantel pamoate: 30% (single dose) and 37% (repeated doses)
- Mebendazole: 19% (single dose) and 45% (repeated doses) [4]

In vitro methods for confirming susceptibility to antihelmintic drugs have not been sufficiently developed and standardized [5]. Although resistance to antihelmintics has already been reported in *A. duodenale*, it has not been fully confirmed to date. In the future, standardized protocols (both in vitro and in vivo) and standardized methods should be used to confirm the resistance of drugs used in the treatment of various helminthiasis. It is reported that resistant or tolerant strains may exist and may emerge more significantly under drug pressure or specific conditions [6]. There is a need for further development of control strategies and, particularly, in vitro testing. The creation of molecular tests and models for antihelmintic resistance is essential to understand its mechanisms. This can be a potential tool for studying the biology of the parasite [7].

The current status and scale of resistance to antihelmintic drugs are still unknown. Helminth drug resistance can be evaluated by the decrease in egg count in feces after treatment and the effect on eggs and larvae. The molecular mechanisms of resistance to levamisole and lactones remain unknown, and it has been shown that resistance to benzimidazoles can be detected using PCR tests [8]. The primary aim is to evaluate the resistance to antihelmintic drugs. The methods available for monitoring resistance are outlined. These include epidemiological, coprological, in vitro methods, molecular tests, and bioanalyses [6]. In human helminthiasis, especially in hookworm infections, reports on drug resistance are comparatively analyzed. The lack of screening tests makes it difficult to study the effectiveness of current antihelmintics. The methods used to evaluate the effect of antihelmintics on helminths are often time-consuming, produce subjective results, and have low sensitivity.

To date, counting helminth eggs in feces (CR) and determining the reduction in egg count (ERR) after treatment with antihelmintic drugs are the most commonly used methods for monitoring drug efficacy in helminthology. The study discusses the amount of sample taken for analysis, the statistical analysis of results, and the host-parasite relationship.

Currently, several coprological diagnostic methods are used to evaluate the susceptibility of antihelmintic drugs. These include the Kato-Miura thick smear method recommended by WHO, flotation techniques, and McMaster's method for counting helminth eggs. The results obtained and the repeatability of the findings in the same fecal sample (FEC) are considered key indicators. According to research, flotation techniques have been found to provide more accurate FEC measurements. In flotation, one egg per gram of feces (EPG) is equivalent, while in the McMaster method, one egg per 20 mg is equivalent to 50 EPG. However, there are no in-depth studies on the analysis of these

methods. The Kato method shows significant differences in the number of egg counts and sample size [9].

When the sample size is small or diagnostic methods are not conducted accurately, there is evidence of low FEC values and inaccuracies in ERR results [10], which is confirmed by statistical modeling results [11]. As a result, there are significant differences in egg excretion rates within the same population. Some helminths do not lay eggs or produce fewer eggs. As a result, low sample sizes or inaccurate diagnostic methods can prevent the accurate assessment of ERR.

Leveckl et al. (2009) suggest that statistical approaches should be implemented considering the accuracy of diagnostic methods and changes in egg quantities.

Statistical Analysis

In statistical analysis, age, gender, and other indicators must be determined, and the degree of overlap of the research results should be evaluated. One factor that can affect treatment effectiveness is the intensity of invasion before treatment. Dobson et al. (2009) argue that ERR, calculated using arithmetic indicators, is the best available method for evaluating drug efficacy and should be used in studies on broad-spectrum antihelmintic treatments.

Before the study, intensity indicators should be determined.

The most suitable test for determining antihelmintic drug susceptibility in human geohelminthiasis will depend on several factors, including the most commonly used drug groups, ease of use for analysis, and which tests will be used. Such tests can only be applied to the infectious stage of the helminths, which occurs after the eggs hatch. This is not relevant for species like *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Trichuris trichiura*. Additional approaches are needed to study the susceptibility of these species to the drugs used.

Conclusion

Recent studies have revealed the development of resistance to antihelmintic drugs. Resistance to specific drugs used for treating human helminthiasis has led to a decrease in effectiveness. In vitro methods for assessing susceptibility to antihelmintic drugs are still underdeveloped and lack standardization. There is no standardized protocol to confirm the existence of resistance to these drugs (in vitro).

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